

Week 2 - Introduction to vector data in QGIS - categorising energy usage globally!

Module Leader: Adam Peacock

Contact email: A.J.Peacock@keele.ac.uk

Week 2 Instructions:

Welcome back!

Last week you created a series of vector files by digitising a base map. This week, you'll be learning more about vector data. As mentioned in the lecture, shapefiles are more than just geometric shapes. We can attribute them with all sorts of properties and values.

This practical today uses data from the World Resources Institute, a database of energy production facilities and power plants. We are going to create a map from this data. Through this processes you will learn:

- How to add CSV (table) data and turn it in to vector data;
- About the properties that can be attributed to vector data (attributes);
- How to sort, organise and select different shapefiles using rules and expressions;
- How to make a basic map using QGIS;

We will also use a shapefile to show planet earth.

Unzip both of these practicals and lets begin.

Part 1 – adding the data:

Firstly, we need to add our data in to QGIS.

1. Go to Layer < add layer < add vector layer and add the *ne_10m_land.shp* file

You will see a new layer ne_10m_land added to the Layers panel.

The global power plant database comes as a CSV file (Comma Separated Vales) so we will need to import it.

2. Click Open Data Source Manager.

Figure 1: Where the Open Data Source Manager tab is located

3. In the Data Source Manager window, switch to the Delimited Text tab.

4. Click the “...” button next to File name and choose to the directory where you extracted the globalpowerplantdatabasev120.zip file.

5. Select theglobal_power_plant_database.csv.

QGIS will auto detect the delimiter and geometry fields.

6. Leave the Geometry CRS to the default value of EPSG:4326 - WGS84. *You'll learn about what this all means next week)*

7. Click Add followed by Close.

Figure 2: The location of buttons/ settings for steps

A new layer global_power_plant_database will be added to the Layers panel and you will see the points representing the power plants in the canvas. Now we are ready to style both these layers.

8. Click the Open the Layer Styling panel button at the top of the Layers panel.

Figure

3: The layer styling options location

The Layer Styling panel will open on the right.

9. Select the ne_10m_land layer first. This will be our base layer so we can keep the styling minimalistic so it is not distracting.

10. Click Simple fill and scroll down.

11. Select a Fill colour (your choice!).

12. Click the drop-down next to Stroke colour and select Transparent Stroke.

This will set the outlines of the land polygons to be transparent. You will see the result of your selection applied immediately to the layer.

Figure 4: the layer styling options.

13. Next select the global_power_plant_database layer.

14. Click on Simple marker and scroll down.

15. Pick a triangle marker.

Figure 5: Layer styling options – triangle marker

16. Scroll up and select a Fill colour of your liking. A useful cartographic technique is to choose a slightly darker version of the fill-colour as the Stroke colour (i.e. the lines).

Good work so far. **SAVE YOUR WORK.**

Part 2: Using shapefile attributes to distinguish data

We can now see where different power plants are geographically located. This is useful... to an extent. There are lots of different types of power plants though. A single symbol rendering of the power plants layer is not very useful. The secret to fixing this lies in a hidden window.

17. Right click on `global_power_plant_database` and click **open attribute table**.

18. The following screen should appear...

The screenshot shows a window titled "global_power_plant_database :: Features Total: 29910, Filtered: 29910, Selected: 0". The table below is the attribute table displayed in the window.

	country	country_long	name	gppd_idnr	capacity_mw	latitude	longitude	primary_fuel	other_fuel1	ot
1	AFG	Afghanistan	Kajaki Hydroele...	GEODB0040538	33	32.322	65.119	Hydro		
2	AFG	Afghanistan	Mahipar Hydro...	GEODB0040541	66	34.556	69.4787	Hydro		
3	AFG	Afghanistan	Naghlu Dam Hy...	GEODB0040534	100	34.641	69.717	Hydro		
4	AFG	Afghanistan	Nangarhar (Dar...	GEODB0040536	11.55	34.4847	70.3633	Hydro		
5	AFG	Afghanistan	Northwest Kabu...	GEODB0040540	42	34.5638	69.1134	Gas		
6	AFG	Afghanistan	Pul-e-Khumri H...	GEODB0040537	6	35.9416	68.71	Hydro		
7	AFG	Afghanistan	Sarobi Dam Hy...	GEODB0040535	22	34.5865	69.7757	Hydro		
8	ALB	Albania	Bistrica 1	WRI1002169	27	39.9116	20.1047	Hydro		
9	ALB	Albania	Fierza	WRI1002170	500	42.2514	20.0431	Hydro		
10	ALB	Albania	Koman	WRI1002171	600	42.1033	19.8224	Hydro		
11	ALB	Albania	Lanabregas	WRI1002172	5	41.3428	19.8964	Hydro		
12	ALB	Albania	Shkopet	WRI1002173	24	41.6796	19.8305	Hydro		
13	ALB	Albania	Ulez	WRI1002174	25	41.6796	19.8936	Hydro		
14	ALB	Albania	Vau i Dijes	WRI1002175	250	42.0137	19.6359	Hydro		
15	ALB	Albania	Vlora	WRI1002176	98	40.4874	19.434	Other		

Figure 6: The attribute table.

Think back to what we discussed in the lecture. Vector data format is really useful because it can hold mass amounts of values, including co-ordinates, locations and

useful facts about the properties of the shapefile. We call these **attributes**. Explore the table and look at the attributes each individual point holds.

Note the latitude and longitude columns. This is how QGIS knew where to locate the points geographically when we imported the data.

19. Close the attribute table once you have explored it fully.

Back to the symbology of our map...

Our map is slowly coming together, but at the moment it doesn't convey much information except the locations of the power plants. You may have noticed the "Primary Fuel" column in the attribute table. This would be a useful way to distinguish between points and show some sort of spatial trend. Let's use a different renderer to make it more useful.

20. Click the Symbology drop-down and select Categorized. Click apply.

Figure 7: The categorised symbol rendering option

The global_power_plant_database layer contains an attribute indicating the primary fuel used in each power plant. We can create a style where each unique fuel type is shown in a different colour.

21. Select primary_fuel as the Column. Click Classify. You will see multiple categories appear and the map rendering change accordingly.

Figure 8: Rendering the map based on the primary_fuel attribute

See how the map changes? You're now telling QGIS to colour the power plants based on the type of fuel source it uses, rather than simply the fact it is a power plant at a particular geographic space. Rather than simply saying where things are, we are starting to explore the attributes of the data and show spatial trends. These attributes can be edited as necessary. However, the map is still quite messy. We can simplify it...

Part 3: Learning SQL – Structured Querying Language:

While a Categorized view is useful, this layer contains too-many categories for one to meaningfully interpret the map. A better approach would be to group certain type of fuel categories and reduce the number of classes we have. We can use **SQL** to do this. SQL refers to the creation of expressions which tell the software how to react with data. It saves **lots** of time to learn to do this. It might seem complicated, but bare with it. Getting the hang of this is really useful!

Let's try to create 3 categories - **Renewable fuel**, **Non-renewable fuel** and **Other**.

22. Open the symbology tab again.

23. Select Rule-based renderer.

24. Select all but one rules by holding the Ctrl key and clicking on each row.

25. Once selected, click the Remove selected rules button to delete them.

Figure 9: Using rule-based rendering

26. Select the remaining rule and click Edit current rule.

Figure 10:
The location of 'edit current rule'

27. Enter Renewable fuel as the Label. Click the Expression button next to Filter.

Figure 11:
The
location
of the
label filter

28. In the **Expression String Builder dialog** (Which you just opened), enter the following expression and click OK. Here we are grouping multiple renewable energy categories into a single category. (You can **try** copying and pasting below into the window)

ATTRIBUTE **FUNCTION** **VALUES**

↓ ↓ ↓

"primary_fuel" IN ('Biomass', 'Geothermal', 'Hydro', 'Solar', 'Wind', 'Storage', 'Wave and Tidal')

If you type this, MAKE SURE IT IS TYPED WITH NO ERRORS.

Think of this as the following sentence, as if you are trying to talk to the software:

"QGIS, **IN** the **primary_fuel** attribute, please select all the points on the map which have the following values: **('Biomass', 'Geothermal', 'Hydro', 'Solar', 'Wind', 'Storage', 'Wave and Tidal')** because I would like to separate these out from the rest of the points on the map and colour them differently"

global_power_plant_database :: Features Total: 29910, Filtered: 29910, Selected: 0

	country	country_long	name	gppd_idnr	capacity_mw	latitude	longitude	primary_fuel	other_fuel1	ot
1	AFG	Afghanistan	Kajaki Hydroele...	GEODB0040538	33	32.322	65.119	Hydro	←	
2	AFG	Afghanistan	Mahipar Hydro...	GEODB0040541	66	34.556	69.4787	Hydro	←	
3	AFG	Afghanistan	Naghlu Dam Hy...	GEODB0040534	100	34.641	69.717	Hydro	←	
4	AFG	Afghanistan	Nangarhar (Dar...	GEODB0040536	11.55	34.4847	70.3633	Hydro	←	
5	AFG	Afghanistan	Northwest Kabu...	GEODB0040540	42	34.5638	69.1134	Gas	✘	
6	AFG	Afghanistan	Pul-e-Khumri H...	GEODB0040537	6	35.9416	68.71	Hydro	←	
7	AFG	Afghanistan	Sarobi Dam Hy...	GEODB0040535	22	34.5865	69.7757	Hydro	←	
8	ALB	Albania	Bistrica 1	WRI1002169	27	39.9116	20.1047	Hydro	←	
9	ALB	Albania	Fierza	WRI1002170	500	42.2514	20.0431	Hydro	←	
10	ALB	Albania	Koman	WRI1002171	600	42.1033	19.8224	Hydro	←	
11	ALB	Albania	Lanabregas	WRI1002172	5	41.3428	19.8964	Hydro	←	
12	ALB	Albania	Shkopet	WRI1002173	24	41.6796	19.8305	Hydro	←	
13	ALB	Albania	Ulez	WRI1002174	25	41.6796	19.8936	Hydro	←	
14	ALB	Albania	Vau i Dijes	WRI1002175	250	42.0137	19.6359	Hydro	←	
15	ALB	Albania	Vlora	WRI1002176	98	40.4871	19.134	Other	✘	

Show All Features

Figure 12: A representation of how the formula selecting the relevant values in the attribute table

You have just created a new category using SQL! It should look like below.

Figure 13: What your formula should look like

29. Click ok.

30. Scroll down and click Simple marker. Choose an appropriate Fill colour. Once done, click the Back button.

Figure 14: Set an appropriate fill colour

SAVE YOUR WORK!

You will see a single rule being applied to the layer for the Renewable fuel category.

We should now differentiate the rest of our data using rules.

31. Right-click the row and choose Copy.

32. Right-click again and choose Paste.

You are simply making another rule. Let's edit it.

Figure 15:
Copying and pasting the rule.

A copy of the existing rule will be added.

33. Select the newly added row and click Edit current rule.

Figure 16:
Edit the second rule

34. Enter Non-renewable fuel as the Label. Click the Expression button next to Filter.

Figure 17: Setting the rule for non-renewable fuels

35. In the Expression String Builder dialog, enter the following expression and click OK.

ATTRIBUTE **FUNCTION** **VALUES**

 "primary_fuel" IN ('Coal', 'Gas', 'Nuclear', 'Oil', 'Petcoke')

“Hi again QGIS, IN the **primary_fuel** attribute, please select all the points on the map which *this time* have the following values: ('Coal', 'Gas', 'Nuclear', 'Oil', 'Petcoke') because I would *again* like to separate these out from the rest of the points on the map and colour them differently”

Figure 18: What your formula should look like for non-renewables

36. Scroll down and click Simple marker. Choose an appropriate Fill colour. Once done, click the Back button.

Figure 19: Set an appropriate marker colour.

37. Repeat the Copy/Paste process to add a third rule. Select it and click Edit current rule.

Figure 20 – making another rule.

38. Enter **Other** as the Label. Choose **“Else - Catch all for other features”** instead of a Filter. This will ensure that any value missed in the previous 2 rules, will be coloured by this rule.

39. Scroll down and click Simple marker.

40. Choose an appropriate Fill colour.

41. Once done, click the Back button.

Figure 21: Setting else for 'other' label

The re-categorisation is complete now. You will see a much cleaner view that shows the distribution of renewable vs. non-renewable fuel sources used by power plants and their distribution across countries.

42. Use the zoom in/ out tools to look around the map and look at the variation. When you are done, right click on the **global_power_plant_database** layer and click zoom to layer. You should have a full perspective of the map!

Final step, make a map!

You have now used the attributes of data to create a map. You should be able to distinguish between each of the different fuel sources used.

To finish this practical off we are going to make a simple map.

43. Go to:

Project < new Print Layout

Don't enter anything for title, click okay (QGIS doesn't give very good title fonts...)

44. Click the button. This displays the full extent of the map.

45. Now add a map:

Figure 22: Adding a map

46. Once add map mode is active, draw a square by holding the left mouse button and dragging. This tells the software where to put a map on your piece of paper.

Figure 23: Drawing a map box

47. The data you just used (Power plants) should appear.

North arrow:

You should also always add a north arrow to a map – it's basic cartography!

48. Go to add item < add Picture.

Draw a smaller box as you did before, hold the left mouse, drag and release. **DON'T MAKE IT TOO BIG!**

49. On the right properties" and (screen shot below)

hand panel, click "item "search directory"

Figure 24: Using search directories to select a north arrow.

Pick something appropriate. The more simplistic a North Arrow, the better your map will look. Outlandish North arrows add unnecessary complexity to a map. A map should always be easy to read and understand.

Now add a scale bar:

50. Add item < add scale bar

51. Again, as above, go to item properties and pick a suitable scale bar. Again – keep it simple! **Set the fixed width to a scale you feel appropriate. Play around until it seems right**

Figure 25: Setting the scale to fixed width.

We should add a legend so that people can understand the map!

52. Add item < add legend

53. Draw the magic box...

54. A legend should appear. Notice how the title of the legend is the file name? You can change this by double clicking where I have highlighted below and changing the name.

Figure 26: Adding a legend

If you scroll down, you can also add a frame by ticking a box..

Figure 27: Adding a frame and background

Finally, lets give our map a title:

55. Add item < add label

56. Again, draw a box.

57. In item properties, expand the “label” section and enter a name. What do you think it should be called?

You can then save your work!

58. Click layout, export as an image and save your work!

You are done. Well done!